

UK Research
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Fisheries and Ocean Carbon in the Celtic Seas – Decision Support Tools and Future Scenarios

29th April 2025, 11.00 – 17.00 CET/10.00 – 16.00 GMT; Online Teams Meeting

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OceanICU Website: <https://ocean-icu.eu/>

Mission Atlantic Website: <https://missionatlantic.eu/>

Marine Beacon Website: <https://marinebeacon.eu/>

Bioprotect Website: <https://bioprotect-project.eu/>

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Executive Summary

The OceanICU project hosted an online stakeholder workshop, on the 29th of April 2025. This workshop focussed on the Celtic Sea shelf fishing community, its interactions with ocean carbon, and getting feedback on the development of future scenarios and the OceanICU Decision Support Tool. It was attended by 15 participants. The workshop had a dedicated half-day to discuss these topics. At the workshop, a series of presentations introduced the OceanICU project; outcomes of previous stakeholder engagements on the topic of ocean carbon; tools (models) being used within the project; the OceanICU Decision Support Tool; and the concept of Ocean System Pathways. In addition, two new projects were introduced: [BioProtect](#), focused on marine biodiversity and protection, and [Marine Beacon](#) focused on bycatch of endangered and protected species. Time was provided for open discussion (Q&A) around the topics presented and formal feedback was obtained through using online Mentimeter polls.

Key outcomes of the workshop included:

- Identification of potential usefulness of the thematic analysis of previous stakeholder engagements for decision making around Marine Protected Areas (MPAs).
- Identification of several key scenarios that can be further developed and tested using ecosystem models. These particularly focussed on scenarios around spatial uses of the sea – conservation and multiple activities, indicating a clear need for modelling to support spatial questions.
- Identification of further data sources that can be used to improve the Celtic Sea Ecopath with Ecosim ecosystem model, but also of data gaps.
- Identification of other uses for the ecosystem models e.g. to support Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) reporting.
- Identification of participant preferences for how to configure the OceanICU Decision Support Tool (DST).
- Identification of the need to characterise the future and the feeling of uncertainty about the future.

The discussions and feedback received from the polls will inform the ongoing research trajectories in the OceanICU project. Future results and outcomes will be reported back to the participants and wider stakeholder group.

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1. Workshop Goals and Set-Up

1.1 Goals

The OceanICU project is focused on better understanding the interactions and potential effects of fishing with ocean carbon and assessing if those effects are large enough to interfere with ocean carbon uptake and affect climate change, and how a range of tools could be used to answer this question. In this workshop we aimed to get **stakeholder feedback on the development of future scenarios and the OceanICU Decision Support Tool** to guide work going forward in the project and ensure relevance of our work to the needs of the fishing industry and society.

This workshop followed on from the previous “**Fisheries; socio-economics, ecosystems, and ocean carbon in the Celtic Seas**” workshop held in March 2024. In that workshop, we discussed the links between fishing, ocean carbon and climate change, gathering stakeholder perceptions on the interactions between fishing activity and ocean carbon.

1.2 Intended Outcomes

During the workshop, we:

- Presented outcomes of the previous stakeholder engagement including stakeholder co-developed conceptual models and emergent themes,
- Showcased tools (models) being used within the project, and gathered feedback on them and their use, inputs, and potential future scenarios,
- Described the development of a Decision Support Tool within OceanICU, and gathered opinions and feedback on user needs and potential applications,
- Introduced the concept of Ocean System Pathways for considering future scenarios,
- Introduced two new relevant projects, [BioProtect](#), focused on marine biodiversity and protection, and [Marine Beacon](#) focused on bycatch of endangered and protected species.

The format of the workshop included a mixture of informative talks and interactive sessions. Through this, the intended outcomes were the identification of relevant management/policy questions and the development of realistic future scenarios to progress towards applied tool development and ensure OceanICU outputs meet stakeholder and end-user needs. We intend to build on the outputs of this workshop with future stakeholder engagement events and workshops.

1.3 Meeting Set-Up

The meeting was hosted online via Teams with collaborative note-taking via a Google document. Additional resources were provided to participants via Google docs and remained available for editing/contributing one-week post-meeting. The meeting was recorded for note-taking purposes (not to be shared). Chatham house rules (information disclosed during a meeting may be reported by those present, but the source of that information may not be explicitly or implicitly identified) was used to ensure open dialogue. Participants were encouraged to contribute with respect in whichever way comfortable (speaking up, posting in the Teams chat, or writing directly in the notes document).

1.4 Participant Profile

A total of 15 individuals attended the workshop (Figures 1.1, 1.2). The workshop was attended by representatives from eNGOs, managers and responsible authorities, advisory bodies, the fishing industry and their representatives, and academia. Participants from academia had the greatest representation at the workshop, forming 33% of the group, followed by those from advisory bodies, responsible authorities/management and eNGOs at 20% each of the group. One individual represented the fishing industry.

Figure 1.1 Participant profile of attendees at the workshop.

Figure 1.2 Shelf Seas Fisheries workshop attendees (for terms see glossary, Appendix 11.2)

2. The OceanICU project

Dr Richard Sanders introduced the OceanICU project. OceanICU is a Pan-European project funded by Horizon Europe and UKRI running from November 2022 to October 2027. It has a consortium of 31 partners across 15 countries. The overall project aim is to produce new data, information and understanding on the role of the ocean in the global carbon cycle. Demands for ocean resources such as food from fish, materials such as trace metals, and blue energy (wind, wave, tidal) are increasing. These increasing demands may affect the uptake of carbon by the ocean due to changes in emissions, industrial processes, and climate change itself. OceanICU recognises the need for knowledge and tools to support decisions makers, managers, and ocean users manage ocean resources, and understand how their interactions with the ocean may affect ocean carbon and hence climate change.

OceanICU is developing new tools that include parameters relevant to management and industry (Figure 2.1). As such, we aim to establish current understanding, perceptions, and needs of stakeholders in relation to oceanic carbon and identify key emerging threats and trajectories. This information will then be used to define scenarios of interest and societal relevance for use in a decision-support tool (DST), and to inform an oceanic carbon risk assessment to enable identification and prioritization of societally relevant carbon-related impacts and threats, scenarios, and trade-offs, and their impacts on associated ecosystem services. As part of this, we will produce a multi-sectoral, multi-pressure oceanic carbon risk assessment to enable identification and prioritization of societally-relevant carbon-related impacts and threats, and their impacts on associated ecosystem services.

Figure 2.1 Overview of processes considered in the OceanICU project.

3. Outcomes from previous stakeholder engagement activities

Dr Fiona Culhane presented outcomes of previous stakeholder engagement, which consisted of a series of workshops and surveys (Box 3.1) designed to get an understanding of current perceptions and understanding of ocean carbon amongst fishing and deep-sea mining industry communities. Participants included those from fishing and mining industries, management/responsible authorities, advisory bodies, academic/researchers and NGOs (Figure 3.1).

Box 3.1 Summary of previous stakeholder engagement activities

FOUR GROUPS	ONLINE WORKSHOP	SURVEY
High Seas Fishing	✔	✔ "High seas fisheries and ocean carbon – An interactive online workshop" (22 participants)
Shelf Seas Fishing	✔	✔ "Fisheries; socio-economics, ecosystems, and ocean carbon in the Celtic Seas" (21 participants)
Deep Sea Mining	✔	✔ "Deep-sea mining and ocean carbon workshop" (21 participants)
Skipper Expo Fishing		✔ Semi-structured interviews (13 participants)

Figure 3.1 Range of participants from each group involved in workshops, surveys and interviews in 2024. See Box 3.1 for number of participants

A conceptual model of the Celtic Seas-Ocean carbon social-ecological system, which was co-produced in a previous workshop with Celtic Seas stakeholders, was sense checked since it was produced. This involved running scenarios to visualise changes resulting from increases or decreases in different elements of the model. As part of the sense check, one change was implemented: The link between species extraction and habitats was removed (see Figure 3.2, Insert, red circle (a)). The rationale for this was that the positive arrow here indicated an increase in species extraction would lead to more habitat or better habitat condition thus, should have been negative. However, having an arrow here at all was considered double counting, because the impact on the habitats from fishing are already considered through the seabed impacts box. The updated model, with this change, was presented during the workshop. A further change (see Figure 3.2, Insert, red circle (b)), was made following this workshop based on stakeholder feedback that the word ‘mariculture’ may be more representative than ‘aquaculture’, hence this was added to the Aquaculture box.

Figure 3.2 Mental model of a shelf seas fishing-ocean carbon social-ecological system, co-produced with stakeholders using the software MentalModeler. The elements of the model are represented as boxes and colour indicates the type of element: sectors (orange), pressures (blue), ecosystem components (yellow), ecosystem services (green), socio-economic elements (pink). Grey boxes are elements that can be mechanisms of change but are not necessarily pressures. Links between the nodes are represented by lines. Lines are either positive (elements are positively correlated; blue lines), negative (elements have an inverse relationship; red lines), or unknown (thin black lines). Insert: provisional model produced during the first workshop in 2024; Main: Final model after consistency checking and presented to stakeholders in the second workshop in 2025.

The survey/interview questionnaire asked seven ranked questions related to understanding of ocean carbon and interaction with industry (Table 3.1). Participants were asked to rate either how important the statement was or how concerned they were, depending on the question (Figure 3.3). There was overall lower concern for organism loss or damage and impacts on the Biological Carbon Pump (BCP); and for seabed impacts from trawling, dredging or mining; there was low-moderate concern about the carbon footprint of fishing or mining; there was slightly higher concern about new or emerging marine activities that have links with carbon; and there was moderate-high concern about the water column plume. Participants assigned moderate-high importance to the links between carbon and fishing (or mining) for understanding the BCP and/or climate change and almost all think that the ocean is very important for managing or improving climate change. In terms of differences in group responses, participants coming from eNGOs mostly responded as very concerned/very important across all questions. Managers and advisory bodies had a more moderate response to most questions, and fishing industry had mixed responses with almost all thinking that the ocean is important or very important for helping us to manage climate change, but most were not concerned about impacts of trawling, impacts of removing organisms or the carbon footprint of fishing, though there was variability in this. Fishing industry were concerned about other marine activities, and especially Offshore Renewable Energy.

Table 3.1 Questions asked to participants of the workshops and interviews with the abbreviation used in Figure 3.3.

Figure abbreviation	Full question asked
Ocean tackling climate change	How important do you think the ocean is for helping us to manage or improve climate change ?
Carbon-industry links	How important are the links between carbon and fishing/mining for understanding the BCP and/or climate change?
Water column plume	How concerned are you about the fact that disturbing the water column through mining activities can (e.g. water plume effects) can cause disruption to the BCP?
New/growing marine activities	How concerned are you about new or growing activities that are related to carbon and climate change?
Carbon footprint	How concerned are you about the carbon footprint of fishing/mining?
Sea-bed impacts	How concerned are you about the fact that bottom trawling/dredging/mining can cause carbon to be released from sediments?
Organism loss and damage	How concerned are you that removing fish, other animals, plants and algae from the ocean removes ocean carbon/ impacts ?

Figure 3.3 Results from questionnaire and interviews. See Table 3.1 for full question. The ‘water column plume’ question was only asked to participants attending the deep-sea mining workshop. Importance or concern goes from 0 - not at all, to 5 - extremely important/concerned.

Finally on the outcomes from previous stakeholder engagements, the results of a thematic analysis were presented (Figure 3.4, Box 3.2). This analysis incorporates some of the key perspectives of the participants who took part in answering the surveys and interviews, as well as those who took part in the discussions during the workshops.

Figure 3.4 Thematic analysis on stakeholder perceptions and understanding of ocean carbon. Note: this work is on-going and the final themes may change.

Box 3.2 Description of themes and subthemes on stakeholder perceptions of ocean carbon. Note: this work is on-going and the final themes may change.

Climate Change

Participants emphasised the need to consider: (1) most climate impacts are coming from land, and therefore ocean based mitigation places an unfair burden on ocean users who may need to change their activities, and (2) any change in ocean activity will have consequences in other ecosystems e.g. less reliance on fish as a low carbon food source would need to be replaced with other protein sources that may have greater impacts on carbon, water and biodiversity.

Care about and valuing the ecosystem

Participants strongly recognised the role of the ocean, biodiversity and habitats in climate regulation, in supplying other ecosystem services and for their intrinsic values. They also expressed concern for ecosystem state for supporting the supply of services and for nature’s sake.

Industry in the wider social-ecological system

Participants spoke about their place in the system in terms of what they provide for society and how they are impacted by factors such as climate change, management and other sectors. Fishing industry stakeholders strongly emphasised that their industry evolves continuously to become more sustainable and mining industry stakeholders also spoke about measures they would take to mitigate impacts.

Participants spoke about how their industry is perceived and the evidence underpinning perceptions, which often makes large assumptions, and is then applied across the sector with no differentiation between activity types. A lack of evidence can result in different groups using this to support their own agendas. There were also perceptions about what management might look like and there was a sense of uncertainty and sometimes fear about the future.

Discussion following the presentation of this work

Participant’s questions and comments are given in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- [In the conceptual model] aquaculture implies finfish farming but mariculture includes seaweed and shellfish farming, and thus is perhaps more useful. For example, aquaculture of seaweed is beneficial compared to finfish aquaculture. “Aquaculture” makes people think of salmon farming.
- Regarding fisheries being under a lot of pressure, data needed on what is being caught. It is difficult to know how much of a future the fishing industry has, especially regarding recruitment. But the industry has resisted full documentation and without knowing what they are catching it is hard to assess.
- How available would the information [survey and thematic analysis] presented be? It is also linked to the MPA process, especially regarding what the fishing industry says about the process. One of the big aspects of the projects would be how do we characterise the future and how do we plan for the future without knowing what will occur. *Information will be made available in anonymous way once written up more systematically. But some information is also provided in the workshop report.*
- Has any research been done with the digital twin? Visualising how scenarios can affect ecosystems through a digital platform. *Will present later in the workshop applications from Digital Twin in the OceanICU decision support tool. We can consider how to use this kind of information within the digital twin.*

4. Ecosystem and Socio-economic Models

4.1 Role of fish and impact of fisheries on the carbon cycle

Dr Paula Silvar presented the development of the application of the Ecopath with Ecosim (EwE) model for investigating the role of fish and impact of fisheries on the carbon cycle. The EwE model has been developed for the Irish Sea and application of this model was greatly improved by incorporating fishers’ knowledge that was gathered through workshops (ICES, 2018; Bentley et al., 2018; 2021). In this new application for the Celtic Sea, Paula sought feedback from participants, using Mentimeter polls, on (1) whether there would be interest in running a similar workshop or other means of gathering fisher’s knowledge; (2) whether the fleet configuration being applied in the model is appropriate (Table 4.1); and (3) the sorts of scenarios that participants would be interested in testing (Table 4.1, Figure 4.1).

Table 4.1 Feedback gathered from participants during the workshop using Mentimeter polls on the configuration of fleets being applied in the EwE model, scenarios of interest to be tested with the model, and other ways the EwE model could be useful for participant needs.

Question asked	Responses
Fleets: Do they make sense to you? Is there anything missing?	Distinction between large, smaller boats or where they operate, i.e., near shore or offshore
	Landings based on 2014 data? Recent data will be quite different e.g. pelagic landings much lower.
What other scenarios are you interested in?	What if future MPA's are no take areas
	Scenarios of increase in protected areas (and in relation to climate change)
	What if marine-based biomaterials were sourced from the ocean, ideally by harvesting existing waste streams?
	What if you incorporated an analysis that also included "suitable areas for possible MPAs" modelled for the Celtic Sea which emerged from the Ecological Sensitivity Analysis 2023-24 published by DHLGH
	The catching of forage fish to feed finfish aquaculture versus encouraging whales and other biodiversity
	Sectoral development and conservation scenarios (in terms of expected spatial demands) and implications for fisheries
	Wind farms as no take zones
	Marine detritus includes too much plastic. clear strategic policies/guidance for multi-use scenarios
How can the Celtic Seas EwE be useful for you?	MSFD D4?
	Providing scenarios and guidance on how we could improve the status and knowledge base around MSFD D1 (non-commercial fish) and D3 Commercial fish and shellfish. Many stocks are unknown or not in GES

Figure 4.1 Feedback gathered from participants during the workshop using a Mentimeter poll on the scenarios of interest to be tested with the EwE model. Participants were asked to rank the scenarios of relevance to them.

Discussion following the presentation of this work

Participant's questions and comments are given in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- Are the data and models shared with the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) reporting, it would tie quite well. *There is a need for food web information there and the Celtic Sea model is being developed right now, so we would be happy if this information is used for the MSFD.*
- In terms of the Irish Sea, I'm not aware of the MSFD being brought into the analytical process or it being compatible with it. With the Celtic Sea it would be useful to incorporate that into the design. Functional groups are brought in via the MSFD framework e.g. wading birds/pelagic birds/demersal fish etc so it would be useful to use that output. Something like WK Celtic Sea would be very useful. Lots of the foodweb work nationally is supported by the Marine Institute and could be progressed in a Celtic Seas version.
- The change in functional groups and making it appropriate to MSFD is sensible but may be a challenge.
- Potting fleet - it would be good to see a breakdown because some fisheries are far more intense than others. Have foreign vessels been included? Post Brexit, we have a massive increase in beam trawling (26 now). *All data from STECF so includes foreign vessels. Post Brexit, we don't have UK data, it is more difficult to include.*
- Offer of data; *if we do workshops that are specific to the Celtic Seas, this would be useful.*
- SSF (small scale fleet) make up 85% of national fleet, probably more fishing hour per annum than rest of fleet combined. *The problem with SSF is the data because some missing from the STECF data. I've looked at sales notes etc to get a coherent picture of effort in Celtic Sea, but ended up surveying number of fishing buoys and where they are at certain times of year and that is the only data to trust.*
- Inshore pair trawling for sprat is something of concern to NGOs for many years and it refers to Ocean carbon. We should be encouraging whales (the whale pump), where there are whales there is a proliferation of phytoplankton at base of food chain and everything that goes along with it, e.g. encouraging planktivorous fish. NGOs have noticed clusters of dead cetaceans and seals in areas where these pair trawlers operate. It's a very small fleet but significant feeding areas for some of the larger whales around Ireland. Also, implication for whale watching tourism. No reference to pair trawlers in this. Comes back to fully documented fisheries and fishing unknown nurseries for commercial fisheries. The people who know what is being caught are fishermen but needs to be recorded. *Data limited, if it's not reported I don't have it. Workshops to complete the development of the model where data is missing would be helpful.*
- In terms of proportion from SSF, we have information too and it's important to drill into that. Anecdotal information from MPA process from BIM regarding ORE engagement through

seafood ORE working group. BIM are advancing that work, some in Celtic Sea. Initial outputs positive, subject to very heavy verification and ongoing.

- Regarding lines do you mean longlines? It is drifting long lines and different kind of lines, it's a group that has more than one line.
- We took the data from 2014. The fish dependent data is quite tricky, prior 2014 it is not published in STECF and after Brexit it is not published either for the UK.
- Based on extracting biomaterials, seagrasses come inshore, using those and how this could have impact, how can we include the opportunities those can bring in the model. In the model that's in detritus but all mixed together, but we could estimate detritus per groups and try to see if you harvest those how that would impact in future scenarios. And for the comment on the forage fish, we were thinking of making scenarios on specific fish and seeing how that influences carbon and we could compare to other things that impact biodiversity. Detritus in the model is what comes from the functional groups so faeces, carcasses, etc.
- A lot of people's concerns are spatial. Spatial models are even more complex and need to have even more data, so it is something to work towards. The EwE must wait until we develop Ecospace and then we'll be able to do spatial management scenarios.
- I've noticed at many advisory councils, that ORE providers and planners saying there won't be no take zones, that fishermen can work amongst the turbines. But trawlers with tangle nets, working through wind farms would be problematic, so ultimately those areas would be no take zones.
- Have been talking to fishing industry about continuous effort in wind farms and it is possible in places like Irish Sea, FU15 etc. If you look at the technology involved and distances between them and if they are designed to allow for trawling corridors etc., it is possible. It is a decision down to individual fishermen if they want to use a trawling corridor or not. But concerns over insurance if fishing in these areas. And fisheries that won't be possible e.g. seine netting, gill netting. But more understanding of what is possible in operational wind farms is ongoing.

4.2 Strath E2E: Current and future applications

Dr Emma Dolmaire presented on another end-to-end ecosystem model, StrathE2E (Heath et al., 2021; StrathE2E App.). This model has been developed for the Celtic Sea region. The model is based on Nitrogen and the team are currently working on developing conversion factors to investigate carbon-based scenarios.

4.3 Combining environmental sciences and economics to promote sustainable ocean management and conservation policy

Dr Fabio Berzaghi presented on a global study of carbon stored in marine sediments and the market value of this (Berzaghi et al., 2025). Using Mentimeter, he sought feedback on finance of ocean management actions, use of ecosystem services approaches and marine carbon dioxide removal (mCDR) strategies (Figure 4.2). Dr Gael Mariani then presented on a global model exploring potential conflicts between fishing activity and carbon sequestration (Mariani et al., 2025).

(a) How does your country/organisation plan to finance ocean management actions?

(b) Is financial valuation of ecosystem services in relation to ecosystem services markets useful for your country/organisation?

(c) Is your country/org interested in developing/promoting marine CDR strategies for funding management actions or as part of climate mitigation?

Figure 4.2 Feedback gathered from participants during the workshop using a Mentimeter poll on (a) finance of ocean management actions, (b) valuation of ecosystem services and (c) marine Carbon Dioxide Removal strategies.

Discussion following the presentation of this work

Participant's questions and comments are given in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- In terms of timescale of impact, if you bottom trawl an area that has never been trawled before, I understand that it is more accessible to be remineralised. How do you account for species already present for a long time? *The first trawling event is potentially the most impacting event, and the impact of subsequent events is probably less significant because the sediment has already been disturbed. If you want to focus on an area, you might be able to take the history of trawling into account.*
- Recent research showed light trawling increased carbon stored in seabed, not reduced. It's complicated. Also, carbon sequestration is often defined as 50 years of storage, so maps showed areas with lots of low retention time, which is likely due to natural processes, as well as fishing, e.g. tides, currents, bioturbation etc. What you are really interested in is what carbon is not in the atmosphere, because then it is sequestered. In the shelf seas it is not sequestered for long on seabed but much more active biologically, therefore putting more carbon back in, speed of circulation in relation to productivity of system possibly more important than total storage time. *I fully agree. The objective was to identify potentially conflicting areas, but that doesn't mean we have a huge impact from bottom trawlers. The next step is to have two scenarios, one with and one without bottom trawling to understand the role of bottom trawling on CO2 emissions. And sometimes it can be a positive relationship. Some models already exist so we can try and use them to answer those questions.*
- What's considered deep trawling and what's considered shallow as there are differences in release rates of carbon? *There is no definition for deep trawling and shallow trawling in our study. Everything is based on the time of sequestration and the deeper, the higher. This means, if you are trawling deep, the probability for the carbon to be re-emitted in the atmosphere is low. In shallow areas the CO2 will probably go to the atmosphere, that's why shallow areas are identified as potentially conflicting.*
- Where do you consider the barrier between shallow and deep, especially in relation to Ireland that has shallow shelf seas and then areas down to abyssal plain? *We don't consider a barrier, we use a model with a coarse resolution with the time sequestration for each scale that were interested in.*

5. OceanICU Decision Support Tool

Dr Jorn Bruggeman presented on the Decision Support Tool being developed in the OceanICU project. As part of this, there are several decisions regarding the utility of the tool and what levers the developers should make available for users. Participants gave feedback through Mentimeter polls on questions related to this that will inform the development of the tool (Figure 5.1).

Figure 5.1 Feedback gathered from participants during the workshop using Mentimeter polls on how users would want to use the OceanICU Decision Support Tool and the types of levers to include.

Figure 5.1 continued Feedback gathered from participants during the workshop using Mentimeter polls on how users would want to use the OceanICU Decision Support Tool and the types of levers to include.

Figure 5.1 continued Feedback gathered from participants during the workshop using Mentimeter polls on how users would want to use the OceanICU Decision Support Tool and the types of levers to include.

6. Ocean System Pathways: Marine industry development under future scenarios

Dr Natalya Gallo presented on Ocean System Pathways, a framework to explore how marine industries will evolve under different socio-economic pathways and climate change (Maury et al., 2017; 2025; O’Neill et al., 2017). As part of this, participants considered the potential for spatial conflicts with four industries that may grow in the future and provided feedback using Mentimeter polls (Figure 6.1).

Figure 6.1 Feedback gathered from participants during the workshop using a Mentimeter poll on spatial conflicts between fishing categories and (a) deep sea mining, (b) offshore wind, (c) dredging, and (d) oil drilling or offshore carbon capture and storage.

Discussion following the presentation of this work

Participant's questions and comments are given in an anonymised form in black text. The response from the OceanICU researchers is given in blue. In some cases, additional information has been added since the workshop, this is indicated in *italics*.

- Could this be used in researching marine biomaterial, promoting harvesting timing. *It's hard to see where the connection point would be for those. The way they have been developed has been for informing more global level policies so not sure how specific questions at regional level, where the connection point would be there.* Do you think it could reveal where marine biomass would accumulate naturally? *No, perhaps other OceanICU models can achieve that.*

7. Introduction to New Projects

Two new projects were introduced to participants:

Ms Maylis Sontot-Marjary introduced the [Bioprotect](#) project, which aims to develop an area-based management decision support framework to support ecosystem based marine spatial planning and preservation of marine and coastal ecosystems. This project includes an Irish demonstration site and will be looking for stakeholder inputs through the research process.

Dr Julia Calderwood introduced the [Marine Beacon](#) project, which is focused on monitoring and elimination of endangered and conserved species in the Northeast Atlantic and High Seas Atlantic region. This project includes an interactive dissemination platform that is hoped will be of use to both researchers and stakeholders, with the facility for 2-way exchange regarding bycatch reduction.

8. Wrap up and final words

In the final part of the workshop, participants were asked to self-reflect on three questions:

- What do you need to know to factor ocean carbon into your work?
- In what ways can it be factored in?
- Where do marine ecosystem carbon functions fit into management or policies e.g. biodiversity, climate, fisheries management, marine management, etc.?

Dr Angela Martin introduced the ICES working group WKFISHCARBON2, and the next steps were covered (included in the action points below).

Action points following the meeting:

- Summary report to be written and circulated for review and feedback. Key messages will be communicated through this report and in other relevant fora.

- More detailed analysis on the survey and thematic analysis will be carried out and participants will be kept updated on outcomes of this.
- The researchers will continue to search for appropriate data sources to inform Celtic Seas models, including contacting and following up on those suggested by participants (BIM, Fishery Liaison). A possibility was raised for the potential for a follow up meeting on Celtic Seas data and ecosystem models. Interest in this will be explored. Researchers also reiterate their appeal to participants to provide any resources they think may be relevant.
- The results from the questions around the Decision Support Tool (DST) will be reviewed and combined with outputs from the high seas and deep-sea mining groups, and researchers will look to incorporate participant preferences in subsequent iterations of the DST.
- For OceanICU, additional follow-up workshops will be arranged with shelf seas, high seas and deep-sea mining stakeholders.
- The first participatory mapping survey will be open for participation from June 30th 2025. The link to the survey will be available on BioProtect's official website and socials. You may also contact the main researcher directly.

9. Conclusions

Active engagement from the invited participants led to a successful outcome for the workshop with valuable information on relevant management/policy questions and information to help the development of realistic future scenarios to progress towards applied tool development and ensure OceanICU outputs meet stakeholder and end-user needs. Outcomes included:

- Identification of potential usefulness of the thematic analysis of previous stakeholder engagements for decision making around MPAs.
- Identification of several key scenarios that can be further developed and tested using ecosystem models. These particularly focussed on scenarios around spatial uses of the sea – conservation and multiple activities, indicating a clear need for modelling to support spatial questions. While our current models are not designed to answer spatial questions, further developments in the EwE model, the StrathE2E model and through the Bioprotect project may help to fill this gap.
- Identification of further data sources that can be used to improve the Celtic Sea EwE model, but also of data gaps in the small-scale fleet and pair trawling.
- Identification of other uses for the ecosystem models e.g. to support MSFD reporting.
- Identification of participant preferences for how to configure the DST.
- Identification of the need to characterise the future and the feeling of uncertainty about the future.

The above points will guide the direction of our research going forward in OceanICU. They will help form the basis of scenarios to test using EwE and a range of other modelling approaches, help to develop the DST, and help to develop future scenarios for ocean system pathways. Future results and outcomes will be reported back to the participants and wider stakeholder group.

10. References

- Bentley, J. W., Serpetti, N., Fox, C., Reid, D., Heymans, J. J. (2018) Modelling the food web in the Irish Sea in the context of a depleted commercial fish community. Part 1: Ecopath Technical Report. Scottish Association for Marine Science, Oban. U.K. Report no. 294, p.147
- Bentley, J.W., Lundy, M.G., Howell, D., Beggs, S.E., Bundy, A., de Castro F., Fox, C.J., Heymans, J.J., Lynam, C.P., Pedreschi, D., Schuchert, P., Serpetti, N., Woodlock, J. and Reid, D.G. (2021) Refining Fisheries Advice With Stock-Specific Ecosystem Information. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 8:602072. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2021.602072
- Berzaghi, F., Pinti, J., Aumont, O. *et al.* Global distribution, quantification and valuation of the biological carbon pump. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* **15**, 385–392 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-025-02295-0>
- Heath, M.R., Speirs, D.C., Thurlbeck, I, & Wilson, R.J. (2021). StrathE2E: an R package for modelling the dynamics of marine food webs and fisheries. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 12, 280-287. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13510>.
- ICES, 2018. Report of the Workshop on stakeholder input to, and parameterization of, ecosystem and foodweb models in the Irish Sea aimed at a holistic approach to the management of the main fish stocks (WKIrish4), 23–27 October 2017, Dún Laoghaire, Ireland. ICES CM 2017/ACOM:54 35.
- Mariani, G., Guet, J., Bianchi, D., DeVries, T., Durfort, A., Barrier, N., Troussellier, M. and Mouillot, D. (2025). Potential conflicts between fishing and oceanic carbon sequestration in 15% of the ocean. *One Earth*, 8, 101245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2025.101245>
- Maury, O., Campling, L., Arrizabalaga, H., Aumont, O., Bopp, L., Merino, G., et al. (2017). From shared socio-economic pathways (SSPs) to oceanic system pathways (OSPs): Building policy-relevant scenarios for global oceanic ecosystems and fisheries. *Global Environmental Change*, 45, 203–216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2017.06.007>
- Maury, O., Tittensor, D. P., Eddy, T. D., Allison, E. H., Bahri, T., Barrier, N., et al. (2025). The Ocean System Pathways (OSPs): A new scenario and simulation framework to investigate the future of the world fisheries. *Earth's Future*, 13, e2024EF004851. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024EF004851>
- O'Neill, B., Kriegler, E., Ebi, K. L., Kemp-Benedict, E., Riahi, K., Rothman, D. S., et al. (2017). The roads ahead: Narratives for shared socioeconomic pathways describing world futures in the 21st century. *Global Environmental Change*, 42(2017), 169–180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.01.004>
- StrathE2E App <https://outreach.mathstat.strath.ac.uk/apps/StrathE2EApp/>

11. Appendices

11.1 Agenda

Time (GMT)	Program
10.00 – 10.20	Introduction to workshop, housekeeping, and OceanICU project
10.20 – 11.15	Follow up on previous workshop outcomes
11.15 – 12.30	Celtic Seas Models and Global Economic Models
12.30 – 13.15	Break
13.15 - 14.15	Decision Support Tools in OceanICU
14.15 – 15.00	Future Scenarios: Shared Socioeconomic Pathways
15.00 – 15.30	Introduction to Bioprotect project
15.30 – 15.50	Introduction to Marine Beacon Project
15.50 – 16.00	Wrap up and final words

11.2 Acronyms

- ABM: Area-Based Management
- BCP: Biological Carbon Pump
- CO2: Carbon dioxide
- DECC: Department of Climate, Energy and the Environment
- DHLGH: Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage
- DST: Decision Support Tool
- EBFM: Ecosystem-Based Fisheries Management
- EBM: Ecosystem-Based Management
- ES: Ecosystem Services
- EwE: Ecopath with Ecosim, ecosystem model
- ICES: International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
- IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
- IWDG: Irish Whale and Dolphin Group
- KFO: Killybegs Fishermen’s Organisation
- mCDR: marine Carbon Dioxide Removal
- MSFD: Marine Strategy Framework Directive

- NWWAC: North Western Waters Advisory Council
- OceanICU: Improving Carbon Understanding
- PPGIS: Public Participation Geographic Information System
- SST: Sea Surface Temperature
- StrathE2E: Strathclyde end to end ecosystem model
- SWAN: Sustainable Water Network
- UCC: University College Cork

11.3 Participant List

List of participants (blue shading indicates OceanICU/workshop organisers)

Name	Organisation
	UCC-MaREI
	Københavns Universitet
	Queens University Belfast
	Killybegs Fishermen's Organisation
	Sustainable Water Network (SWAN)
	DECC
	Irish whale and dolphin group
	North Western Waters Advisory Council
	Irish Seal Sanctuary
	Heriot-watt University
	Fishery Liaisons Limited (DECC)
	Marine Environment, Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage
	Arup
	Queen's University Belfast
	Department of Housing Local Government and Heritage
Emma Dolmaire	University of Strathclyde
Fabio Berzaghi	WMU
Fiona Culhane	Marine Institute
Gael Mariani	WMU
Jorn Bruggeman	Bolding & Bruggeman ApS
Julia Calderwood	Marine Beacon
Maylis Sontot-Marjary	Marine Institute
Natalya Gallo	Norce
Paula Silvar	Marine Institute
Richard Sanders	Norce
David Reid	ICES
Angela Martin	Natural England

11.4 Resources

- BioProtect project website: [Home - BioProtect](#)
- Guo, J., Brugel, S., Andersson, A., & Lau, D. C. P. (2022). Spatiotemporal carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus stoichiometry in planktonic food web in a northern coastal area. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2022.107903>
- Heath, M.R., Benkort, D., Brierley, A.S. *et al.* Ecosystem approach to harvesting in the Arctic: Walking the tightrope between exploitation and conservation in the Barents Sea. *Ambio* **51**, 456–470 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-021-01616-9>
- ICES workshop on Assessing the Impact of Fishing on Oceanic Carbon (WKFISHCARBON; outputs from 2023 meeting): https://ices-library.figshare.com/articles/report/Workshop_on_Assessing_the_Impact_of_Fishing_on_Oceanic_Carbon_WKFISHCARBON_outputs_from_2023_meeting_/24949122
- Laverick, J. H., Speirs, D. C., & Heath, M. R. (2025). Sea-Ice Retreat From the Northeast Greenland Continental Shelf Triggers a Marine Trophic Cascade. *Global Change Biology*, 31(4), e70189. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.70189>
- Mentimeter polls: www.mentimeter.com
- OceanICU Decision Support Tool prototype: <https://ocean-icu.lab.dive.edito.eu/>
- OceanICU webinars (including Fish, Fisheries and Carbon webinar): <https://ocean-icu.eu/webinars/>
- OceanICU: <https://ocean-icu.eu/>
- Stakeholder Mailing List Sign Up for OceanICU <https://tinyurl.com/OceanICUjoin>
- StrathE2E App: <https://outreach.mathstat.strath.ac.uk/apps/StrathE2EApp/>
- Thorpe RB, Arroyo NL, Safi G, Niquil N, Preciado I, Heath M, Pace MC and Lynam CP (2022) The Response of North Sea Ecosystem Functional Groups to Warming and Changes in Fishing. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 9:841909. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.841909>
- Tray, E., Huck, J., Hickey, J., Daly, S. and Cosgrove, R. (2025) Participatory mapping of small fishing vessel activities for marine spatial planning. BIM. <https://bim.ie/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Final-participatory-mapping-report-1.pdf>
- WKFISHCARBON2 on ICES website <https://www.ices.dk/community/groups/Pages/WKFISHCARBON2.aspx>